

NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites catalyzed degradation of reactive dyes in presence of oxidants under UV-Visible radiation

Santhanam Sivakumar^a, Ayyasamy Selvaraj^b, Venkadachalam Chandrasekaran and Anaipalayam Kandasamy Ramasamy^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Periyar University, Salem-636 011, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drakramasamy@yahoo.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Hindustan Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : Ilmenite NiTiO₃ and Wurtzite ZnO have been synthesized by sol-gel route. A series of NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composite photocatalysts with a different weight ratio of NiTiO₃ (3 wt%, 5 wt%, 7 wt%, 9 wt% and 11 wt%) were prepared by the coupling of NiTiO₃ and ZnO with the help of oxalic acid as a linker. The obtained NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites of crystalline phase and optical properties were investigated by using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and UV-Vis diffused reflectance spectroscopy (DRS). The photocatalytic activity of NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites was carried out on the degradation of reactive dye such as reactive blue 4 (RB 4) under UV-Visible light irradiation. 9 wt% NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites demonstrate higher photocatalytic activity than that of other heterojunction composites and parent photocatalyst like ZnO and NiTiO₃ at pH 5. The addition of substantial amount of electron acceptors such as H₂O₂ and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ increases the rate of degradation of RB 4 on 9 wt% NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composite. Further, the electron acceptors (oxidants) used for degradation of the other four different structured reactive dyes in the presence NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites. The extent of mineralization on these organic reactive dyes during photocatalytic degradation was estimated from COD analysis. NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction photocatalyst was also found to have good photostability in the presence of electron acceptors.

Keywords : NiTiO₃/ZnO, oxidants, photocatalytic efficiency, UV-Visible light.

Introduction

Large amounts of dyes are annually produced and applied in different industries including textile, paper, cosmetic, leather, pharmaceutical and nutrition industries¹. Particularly reactive azo dyes are widely used in the dyeing purpose because of its simple dyeing procedure. These azo dyes are resistant to biodegradation and hence, conventional biological treatment methods are ineffective to decolorize². Because the reactive azodyes having moieties like chlorotriazine, vinyl sulphone, dichloroquinoline and etc., are reported to be more difficult to get degraded by in this methods due to their high stability. Further the partially degraded intermediate such as aromatic amines and amides to causes the carcinogenic problem.

Nowadays, semiconductor photocatalytic oxidation has been widely used for the treatment of many organic reactive dyes, which can be expediently applied to dye pollut-

ants for their degradation. Among the various semiconductor materials, ZnO is an ideal material due to its high UV activity and low cost. Further, it also produces photogenerated holes with high oxidizing power due to its high photosensitivity and faster electron transfer to molecular oxygen³. The potential application of ZnO in photocatalysis has aroused great attention, since there are several examples of nanostructure ZnO presenting higher photocatalytic activity than the widely investigated TiO₂⁴.

This organic reactive dyes such as reactive blue 4, reactive black 5, reactive red 120, reactive orange 30 and reactive yellow 84 of the λ_{max} is 598, 603, 517, 420 and 410 nm respectively. These dyes have a strong light absorption in UV-Visible region. The UV-Visible transmittance spectrum of the reactive dyes shows that more than 70% of incident light in the wavelength range 200–610 nm was absorbed by 100 mg L⁻¹ dye solution in a path length of 1 cm. Hence, the degradation of the RB 4 solu-

tion with concentration above 100 mg L⁻¹ in a simple photocatalytic process over a UV active photocatalyst like ZnO is difficult and will take more treatment time for complete degradation.

Hence, coupling of ZnO with a suitable semiconductor is an effective method to utilization of visible light and also accelerate the separation of the generation of the electron (e⁻)-hole (h⁺) pairs because the energy gap between the two semiconductors would benefit the separation of photogenerated electrons and holes. Therefore, many heterostructure photocatalysts with high photocatalytic activity have been investigated, such as CdS/ZnO, NaNbO₃/ZnO and others has been investigated by researchers^{5,6}. In this paper, we have reported the preparation and activity of NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites for degradation of reactive dyes in the UV-Visible radiation.

Experimental

Preparation of heterojunction composite photocatalyst :

Synthesized pure Wurtzite ZnO was used to fabricate the NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composite structure with ilmenite NiTiO₃. For the preparation of 3% NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composite, 0.03 g of NiTiO₃ was first added to 40 ml of ethanol, to that 0.2750 g of oxalic acid was added and the mixture was stirred in a magnetic stirrer to form a homogeneous suspension. To that suspension, 0.97 g of ZnO was added and the stirring was continued for 12 h. Then the suspension was dried and subsequently annealed at 300 °C for 3 h in a muffle furnace. The final product obtained was labelled as NZ 3. Similarly, 5, 7, 9 and 11 wt% of NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites were prepared by varying FeTiO₃ and ZnO ratios and were labelled as FZ 5, FZ 7, FZ 9 and FZ 11 respectively.

Experimental setup for photocatalytic studies in UV-Visible light :

The cylindrical homemade (15 cm × 20 cm) photoreactor setup was used for the photocatalytic studies under UV-Visible radiation. The reactor was illuminated by a 500 W tungsten halogen lamp, and the temperature of the reactor was maintained by continuous circulation of water in its outer jacket. In a typical experi-

ment, 50 ml of 50 mg/L of dye solution was taken with 50 mg of photocatalyst in the photoreactor. Then the lamp was switched on, and the concentration of the dye was measured periodically by measuring the light absorbance of the solution at the λ_{\max} of the dye using Elico UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The effects of oxidants were studied in the similar manner with the addition of calculated quantities of 1 M oxidants solution into the dye solution before turning on the lamps.

Results and discussion

Characterization of FeTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites :

Fig. 1(a) presents the X-ray diffraction pattern of NiTiO₃, ZnO, NZ 3, NZ 5, NZ 7, NZ 9 and NZ 11. Patterns of NiTiO₃ match the JCPDF card No. 71-2195 and ZnO could be perfectly indexed with JCPDS 36-145. However, in all the NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites, diffraction peak of the NiTiO₃ was not observed, which may be due to the low concentration of NiTiO₃ coupled with ZnO.

Fig. 1(b) shows the UV-Visible diffused reflectance spectra of NiTiO₃, pure ZnO and NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites. NiTiO₃ synthesized in this method shows strong absorbance in the visible light range of 410–495 nm. The absorbance onset of as-synthesized Wurtzite ZnO was 390 nm which corresponding to a band-gap of 3.19 eV. The absorbance onset of ZnO in NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction was slightly shifted to longer wavelength. Hence, small amount of NiTiO₃ has been coupled with high crystalline ZnO. So that, ZnO absorbance peak only dominates in UV-Visible absorption spectrum of NiTiO₃/ZnO. Finally from the result, NiTiO₃ not only shift the longer wavelength, its mainly act as electron receiver when the coupling with ZnO.

Photocatalytic degradation RB 4 :

The photocatalytic degradation of reactive blue 4 (RB 4) on pure ZnO, NiTiO₃ and NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites in the presence of UV-Visible light irradiation are shown in Fig. 2(a). The photocatalytic activity of NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites was higher than that of the pure ZnO photocatalyst and the order of activity of heterojunction composites was found to be ZnO < NZ 3 < NZ 5 < NZ 7 < NZ 11 < NZ 9. The increase

Fig. 1. (a) XRD patterns and (b) UV-Visible DRS spectra of NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composites.

in photocatalytic activity of ZnO on heterojunction with NiTiO₃ might be due to the inhibition of electron-hole recombination by a charge separation mechanism. However, by increasing the NiTiO₃ content to an optimum level (NZ 9), the photocatalytic activity decrease due to the diffusion of NiTiO₃ which obviously becomes poor and the redundant NiTiO₃ can act as recombination centers, resulting in the slower transformation of the photo-induced electrons, so as decreasing the photocatalytic activity⁷.

Effect of addition of oxidants :

In the heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation pro-

cess, addition of suitable external oxidants to the molecular oxygen supported dye solutions should enhance the photocatalytic efficiency. The enhancement of degradation by the addition of oxidants such as H₂O₂ and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ is due to the increase in the production of hydroxyl radical (•OH).

The effect of addition of oxidants such as H₂O₂ and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ has been investigated by varying the amount of oxidants from 0 mM to 25 mM on the NZ 9. The results are shown in Fig. 2(b).

The degradation of RB 4 has been increased from 64% to 100%, with the addition of oxidants from 0 to 20

Fig. 2. (a) Photocatalytic degradation of RB 4 and (b) photocatalytic efficiency of NZ 9 at different (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ and H₂O₂ concentration on RB 4.

mM. This dye degradation was found to be enhanced by the inhibition of electron-hole recombination contributed by the abstraction of photoexcited electrons and production of •OH radical⁸.

The optimum concentration of (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ for the degradation of dye over NZ 9 was found to be 10 mM. Further, increase in (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ dosage has no significance on the degradation of dye, since the excess of SO₄⁻ ion formed was being adsorbed on the photogenerated holes and by the hydroxyl radicals as given in eqs. (1) and (2). Similarly, at high H₂O₂ dosage (25 mM) the dye degradation efficiency decreases due to the reaction of •OH radical with the H₂O₂ and also with •OH radical and produces weaker •OOH radical rather than dye molecule as expected (3 and 4). This weaker hydroperoxy radical do not contribute in the degradation of organic dyes.

Degradation of other reactive dyes :

The photodegradation efficiency of NiTiO₃/ZnO composites on other reactive dyes with different chemical structure were also studied in the presence of oxidants (H₂O₂ and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈). This result is given in Fig. 3 (a). The dyes chosen for this study are Reactive Black 5 (RB 5), Reactive Orange 30 (RO 30), Reactive Yellow 84 (RY 84) and Reactive Red 120 (RR 120). The initial concentration of all the dye solutions were 50 mg/L and

dosage of photocatalyst was 0.5 g/L. From the results, the photodegradation rate of dyes was arranged in the following increasing order as RB 5 > RO 30 > RY 84 > RR 120 for both oxidants. However, the above order was observed, very quickly when carried out in presence of (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ (120 min) due to the procreating capacity of peculiar oxidizing agents like •OH and SO₄^{•-}. Thus the rate of degradation of RB 5 was the fastest and RR 120 was slowest among the dyes, as observed in the case of both oxidants. The degraded reactive dyes solution was tested by COD analysis. From the analysis, RB 5, RO 30, RY 84 and RR 120 COD values are (81, 75, 61, 52 and 44%) and (76, 61, 50, 42 and 33%) in the presence of (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ and H₂O₂ respectively. Apart from degradation, the photocatalytic process leads to a substantial decrease in the COD values of the solution. Therefore, COD reduction value is less than percentage of degradation, which may be due to the formation of smaller uncolored intermediates. Therefore, it seems that to achieve complete mineralization of dyes, a longer irradiation time is required.

Testing of photostability :

The NZ 9 heterojunction composite was found to have good photostability in the presence of (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ and H₂O₂; the material retains almost 89% and 84% of activity even in the fifth cycle, because oxidants could sufficiently abstract the photogenerated electrons. The slight decrease in the activity of the NZ 9 after each run may be due to the catalytic poison of photocatalyst by intermediates strongly adsorbed on the surface.

Fig. 3. (a) Photocatalytic degradation efficiency of NZ 9 heterojunction composite for different structured organic reactive dyes in presence of oxidants and treatment time 60 min and (b) photostability of NZ 9 heterojunction photocatalyst.

Conclusion

NiTiO₃/ZnO heterojunction composite have been found to show good photocatalytic activity for the degradation of reactive blue 4. NZ 9 showed better photocatalytic activity than other heterojunction composites. Further addition of electron acceptors such as H₂O₂ and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ enhanced the photocatalytic efficiency of NZ 9 as expected. Mineralization studies have shown that (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ exhibit higher COD value compared to that of H₂O₂. NZ 9 heterojunction composite also degraded other dyes with different chemical structures, such as RB 5, RO 30, RY 84 and RR 120. The NZ 9 heterojunction composite has good photostability in the presence of oxidants (H₂O₂ and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈). Among the two oxidants, (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ was the good candidate for the photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes than that of H₂O₂.

References

1. L. G. Devi, S. G. Kumar, K. M. Reddy and C. Munikrishnappa, *Desalin. Water Treat.*, 2009, **4**, 294.
2. B. Pare, S. B. Jonnalagadda, H. Tomar, P. Singh and V. W. Bhagwat, *Desalination*, 2008, **232**, 80.
3. Chia-Yun Chen, Meng-Cheng Cheng and Arh-Hwang Chen, *J. Environ. Manag.*, 2012, **102**, 125.
4. C. Lizama, J. Freer, J. Baeza and H. D. Mansilla, *Catal. Today*, 2002, **76**, 235.
5. P. Kundu, P. A. Deshpande, G. Madras and N. Ravishankar, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2011, **21**, 4209.
6. H. Xu, C. Liu, H. Li, Y. Xu, J. Xia, S. Yin, L. Liu and X. Wu, *J. Alloys and Compnds.*, 2011, **509**, 9157.
7. M. Sun, G. Chen, Y. Zhang, Q. Wei, Z. Ma and B. Du, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2012, **51**, 2897.
8. M. Saquib and M. Munner, *Dyes Pigm.*, 2002, **53**, 237.